

Notas breves

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PALABRAS CLAVE: *Circulus philippinensis*, *Circulus pacomartinezi*, nomen novum.

After the publication of our book on Indo-Pacific Vitrinellidae (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2022a) and the detection of one case of homonymy among the species described therein (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2022b), we noticed a further error by giving the specific name *Circulus philippinensis* to another of the newly described species of *Circulus* (RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2022a: 16, 359).

SHUTO (1969: 54-56, pl. 1, figs. 9-11) described *Pygmaeorota* (*Lydiphnopsis*) *philippinensis*. Subsequently, PONDER (1994) and RUBIO & ROLÁN (2022: 16) considered *Lydiphnopsis* synonymous

with *Circulus*. Therefore, *Circulus philippinensis* (Shuto, 1969) is a valid species and the name of the new species described by RUBIO & ROLÁN (2022, pag. 359) as *Circulus philippinensis* is preoccupied. It is therefore invalid and the species must receive a new name.

We propose *Circulus pacomartinezi* as nomen novum for *Circulus philippinensis* Rubio & Rolán, 2022 (page 359, Fig. P5), non *Circulus philippinensis* (Shuto, 1969) (Fig. 1). The new specific name honours Francisco Martinez Lopez "Paco", mineralogist and good friend of the first author.

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Figure 1. *Circulus pacomartinezi* nomen novum for *C. philippinensis* Rubio & Rolán, 2022. A-C: holotype, 4.77 mm in diameter. Philippines, N Mindoro, 13°28.0'N-121°12.0'E, 155-167 m; MNHN-IM-2000-37569; D, E: protoconch and detail; F: sculpture (reproduced from RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2022a, p. 359).

Figure 1. *Circulus pacomartinezi* nomen novum para *C. philippinensis* Rubio & Rolán, 2022, página 359. A-C: holotipo, 4.77 mm de diámetro. Filipinas, N Mindoro, 13°28.0'N-121°12.0'E, 155-167 m; MNHN-IM-2000-37569; D, E: protoconcha y detalle; F: escultura (reproducido de RUBIO & ROLÁN, 2022a, p. 359).